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Research Article

**RELIABILITY OF FINE NEEDLE ASPIRATION CYTOLOGY
IN PATIENTS WITH PALPABLE BREAST LUMPS**¹Dr Mahwish Kulsoom, ²Dr Ameena Zahid, ³Dr Ammara Tahir¹Nishtar Medical University and Hospital, Multan²Nishtar Medical University and Hospital, Multan³Nishtar Medical University and Hospital, Multan**Article Received:** June 2020**Accepted:** July 2020**Published:** August 2020**Abstract:**

Objective: To assess the accuracy of diagnostic cytology of fine needle aspiration [FNAC] in patients with a palpable breast lump by taking histopathology as a gold standard.

Study project: A Cross-sectional examination.

Setting: -General Surgery Department, Nishtar Hospital, Multan for one-year duration from March 2019 to March 2020.

Material and methods: All patients aged 30-55 years who presented a breast lump with a recent onset that meet the criteria for excluding inclusion have been allowed. A total of 74 patients were included in the study.

Results: - Most of the 40 patients were observed in the age group 41-50 years. Pathologists were unable to make a diagnosis in 10 shifts. Histopathological reports showed that 50 lesions out of 74 were mild because 24 were malignant. Of the mild 22 lesions were Fibroadenoma, 18 were fibrocystic diseases, 8 were chronic pyogenic mastitis and two cases of tuberculosis were diagnosed. In 24 cases of malignancy, 13 cases of invasive ductal cancer and 11 cases of intra-wire cancer were reported.

Conclusion: FNAC is a patient-friendly, easy, reliable, repeatable and simple diagnostic test. According to an expert pathologist, FNAC diagnostic accuracy is very high.

Keywords: Cytology of thin needle aspiration, fibroadenoma, pyogenic mastitis.

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INTRODUCTION:

A breast lump is a common surgical problem in women. In Pakistan, fibroadenoma (25%) followed by fibrous disease (22%), cancer (18.7%), inflammatory changes (18%) gynecomastia (11.2%) different conditions (5.1%). Breast cancer is the most common cancer in women, covering 30% of all cancers in women. The incidence of breast cancer increases in most populations. In developing countries, breast cancer accounts for 1-3% of deaths. In Pakistan, breast cancer is ranked number one for cancer in women. A surgical biopsy of a palpable breast lump has been considered the gold standard for the diagnosis of a breast lump(s). Emphasis was placed on improving the method of establishing a final diagnosis of breast mass before surgery. Different Fine needle aspiration cytology (FNAC) is currently the most popular single modality for diagnosing various lumps of breasts. The absence of false positives unequivocally confirms its place not only as a free supplement, but also as a substitute for biopsy notches in most cases. It is relatively inexpensive and can be performed by hand or with image guidance (ultrasound or stereotactic). It can be safely carried out as a preoperative diagnostic method in patients with breast lumps, mainly in the outpatient ward. Since the breast lump is a common and serious problem, we conducted a study to measure the reliability of FNAC in palpable breast lumps, comparing its result with the gold standard of open biopsy/histopathology in our environment and obtaining local data to assess its effectiveness.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

This cross-cutting, non-probability, purposive study was conducted at the General Surgery Department, Nishtar Hospital, Multan for one-year duration from March 2019 to March 2020 on 74 patients. The study included all patients aged 30 to 55 years with a breast lump at the last start (i.e. within the last month). All male patients with breast lumps, breast abscess and nursing mothers were excluded from the study.

Data collection procedure: Performa Specialized Company is designed to record results. The Institute's Ethics Committee has been approved. Informed consent was given to patients, ensuring confidentiality, describing the procedures and facts that there was no risk to patients in the study. All patients with a breast lump, meeting the criteria for

inclusion present in the outpatient ward, were admitted to the ward. All patients were sent to FNAC for a cyto-pathologist at Nishtar Hospital. FNAC has been marked as positive if it confirms the presence of cancer cells. Histopathology results were evaluated independently of FNAC results. Later, FNAC sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value and negative predictive value were calculated compared to histopathology results. The data was analyzed using the SPSS-18 computer program. Descriptive statistics were used to calculate the mean and standard deviation for age and duration of complaints. Sensitivity and specificity were calculated using the following formula: - Sensitivity = $TP / (TP + FN) \times 100$ Specific = $TN / (TN + FP) \times 100$ Positive predictive value and negative predictive value were calculated using the following formula:- Positive predictive value = $TP / (TP + FP)$ Negative predictive value = $TN / (TN + FN)$ [TP = positive truth, TN = true negative, FP = false positive, FN = false negative]

RESULTS:

FNAC results were respectively recorded with C2 to confirm mild and C5 to confirm malignant. Most of the 40 (54%) patients were observed in the 41-50 age group. The minimum duration was 8 days, while the maximum was 30 days. The average duration of the presentation of the complaint was 20.88 out of 6.14. According to the FNAC analysis, a conclusive diagnosis of malignant tumor was made in 24 patients, while 40 lesions were marked as benign. Diagnosis of 10 lesions has not been confirmed and a true-cut biopsy or punch biopsy was recommended. These smears have been classified as unsatisfactory. Histopathological reports showed that 50 lesions out of 74 were mild because 24 were malignant. Of the mild 22 lesions were Fibroadenoma, 18 were fibrocystic diseases, 8 were chronic pyogenic mastitis and two cases of tuberculosis were diagnosed. In 24 cases of malignancy, 11 cases of invasive ductal cancer and 13 cases of intra-wire cancer were reported. Positive predictive value and negative predictive value of benign lumps Positive predictive value (PPV) = 100 Negative predictive value (NPV)=71% FNAC sensitivity for malignant papules. Positive predictive value and negative predictive value of malignant lumps Positive predictive value (PPV) = 100 Negative predictive value (NPV) = 100.

Histopathological diagnosis (n=74)

Diagnosis	=n	%age
Benign	50	67.6
Fibroadenoma	22	44
Fibrocystic disease	18	36
Ch-pyogenic mastitis	08	16
Tuberculosis	02	04
Malignant	24	32.4
Intraductal carcinoma	11	45.83
Invasive ductal carcinoma	13	54.16

Comparison of FNAC and histopathology for diagnosis of benign breast diseases**DISCUSSION:**

The current study included 74 patients. FNA detected 24 out of 24 malignancies (100%). Of these 24 malignancies, 13 were invasive ductal cancer and 11 were intraductal cancer and there was no false positive and FNAC accuracy was

100%. In this study, an analysis of cytological reports showed that for most lesions, the pathologist can make the correct diagnosis, except for changes with acellular smear. The lowest diagnosis rate was observed in chronic pyogenic mastitis. Pathologists were reluctant to make a

diagnosis of chronic breast inflammation in two cases and requested an open biopsy. For 50 changes marked by histopathology as a mild diagnosis of FNA 40 (80%) and 10 (20%) marked as unsatisfactory in diagnosis. Among these 40 cases, FNAC can diagnose 20 Fibroid adenoma, fibrocystic disease at 15, chronic pyogenic mastitis in 4 and tuberculous mastitis in 1. Analysis of various analytical data on fnac performance and reliability showed a sensitivity of 100%, a specificity of 100% diagnostic accuracy of 83.3%, a false positive rate of 0% and a false negative rate of 0%. These results are roughly similar to other such studies comparing FNAC with histopathology. While the fnac sensitivity to malignant papules in our study was 100%, the absolute value of 90.9% was obtained by the Hussain ET series et a. In a series of 100 patients, Dennison reported fnac sensitivity as 90.4%, while Wu et al. compared the results of postoperative pathology and showed a sensitivity of 75% to FNAC, while a true cut biopsy showed a sensitivity value of 92% and a frozen 100% section. Westend et al represented a value of 92% for FNAC, which was slightly lower than our findings. As already mentioned above, the positive and negative predictive values of the test are those that measure the effectiveness of the test by measuring its "predictive value", which reflects the diagnostic power of the test. They depend on the sensitivity, specificity and incidence of diseases. As a result, Franco et al, in his study of 300 patients on FNAC usability, reported a positive predictive value of 100% and a negative predictive value of 92%. A very large study of 1,297 patients conducted by Choi et al, on FNAC correlation and histopathological reports, showed that the positive predictive value was 98.4% and the negative predictive value was 88%. It is clear that our results fit well with the results of previous studies reported in the literature. In trying to find the cause of the change in value in some studies, we felt that the most common cause was probably related to the expertise of the person performing the aspirations. The maximum differences in terms of lower values were in sensitivity. With the FNAC execution procedure fairly standardized already in all institutions, the only important variable remains the person performing the real aspirations. In such a scenario, the procedure itself should not be distorted, and a myriad of studies carried out in this aspect indicate that this factor is taken into account when such studies are interpreted and reported. In our study, the consistently high values of all parameters were most likely due to the fact that, as mentioned earlier, only pathologists with at least five years of experience performed aspirations. In this way, the main obstacle to achieving better results is removed and a better cytohistological correlation is obtained. In a similar study

conducted by Hussain in 50 patients, the age distribution ranged from fifteen to sixty-five years, and the maximum number of patients was observed in the thirty-one to forty-year-olds (30%). Similar studies conducted by Homesh et al and Tiwari have shown similar age patterns. Patel et al showed that FNAC results were influenced by the number of needle maneuvers performed with less than ten needle maneuvers associated with a 54% unsatisfactory aspiration rate, compared to 25%, when more than ten maneuvers were carried out. They concluded that experience and technique are the most important factors in obtaining a satisfactory aspirate from breast nodules. Ljung et al also reported on the impact of training and experience in breast aspiration cytology with maximum impact on sensitivity values, which plummeted from 98.2% to 75% with an untrained aspiring person.

CONCLUSIONS:

The cytology of thin needle aspiration is a patient-friendly, easy, reliable, repeatable and simple diagnostic test. In the performance of an expert cytopathologist, the diagnostic accuracy of FNAC is very high. High sensitivity and high positive predictive value have shown that positive FNAC in the breast means a clear diagnosis of a given pathology compared to the final histological report. High specificity and high negative predictive value for cancer illustrate the high accuracy of FNAC in the diagnosis of cancer in the breast. Importantly, the negative report on malignancies was very accurate (>92%) in predicting the absence of malignant tumors. Thus, we do not hesitate to conclude that FNAC is a very important preliminary diagnostic test in palpable breast nodules, and made by the hands of experts, the results show a high degree of correlation with the final histopathology report.

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